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Jimenez, M., Montoro, P. R., & Luna, D. (2017). Global shape integration and illusory form perception in the absence of awareness. *Consciousness and Cognition*, 53, 31-46. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.CONCOG.2017.05.004>

Global shape integration and illusory form perception in the absence of awareness.

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Running head: Perceptual Organization without awareness

Abstract

Previous research on perceptual organization operations still provides contradictory evidence on whether the integration of sparse local elements into coherently unified shapes and the construction of the illusory form are accomplished without the need of awareness. In the present study, three experiments were conducted in which participants were presented with masked (Experiment 1, SOA = 27ms; Experiment 2; SOA = 53ms) and unmasked (Experiment 3) *primes* consisting of geometric shapes (a square or a diamond) that could be congruent or incongruent with a subsequent *probe* stimuli (square vs. diamond). Furthermore, the primes were divided into: a *grouping condition* (where local elements may group together into global shapes), an *illusory condition* (where the arrangement of local elements produced illusory shapes) and a *hybrid condition* (where both operations were presented simultaneously). While no priming effects were found for the shortest SOA (27 ms), both *grouping* and *illusory* primes produced significant priming effects in the longer SOA (53 ms). On the other hand, results in Experiment 3 (unmasked) showed strong priming effects for the grouping of the inducers in both the *grouping* and the *hybrid* conditions, and also a significant but weaker priming effect for the *illusory* condition. Overall, our results support the possibility of the integration of local visual features into a global shape in the absence of awareness and, likewise, they suggest an early –subliminal– construction of the illusory shape, implying that feedback projections from higher to lower visual areas are not crucial in the construction of the illusory form.

Keywords: awareness, grouping, illusory form, priming, perceptual organization, subliminal.

1. Introduction

Perceptual organization operations (i.e. contour processing, grouping operations, figure-ground segmentation or modal/amodal completions) are responsible for the structuring of pieces of visual information into larger units of perceived objects and their interrelations (Palmer, 1999, pp. 255). This structuring, however, is a complex task better explained as a hierarchy of visual processes divided into different perceptual stages (Marr, 1982; Palmer, 2015), where different perceptual organization operations might be accomplished at different processing levels: some rapidly in early perceptual stages, others involving later processing in higher tier visual areas of the ventral stream (Behrmann & Kimchi, 2003).

Furthermore, studies investigating the perceptual organization process at the mid-level stage often confront one of the most fascinating phenomena in visual perception: the emergence of visual consciousness. Thus, while it is commonly assumed that low-level visual operations are mostly accomplished in the absence of awareness, studies involving mid-level visual processes (such as form perception) are often focused on determining the extent of the involvement of visual consciousness on its completion.

Not surprisingly, previous studies on mid-level perceptual operations have tried to understand how and when unified global shape percepts arise from the integration of separate local elements, yet results still provide contradictory evidence on whether these operations are accomplished with or without the need of perceptual awareness.

Montoro, Luna and Ortells, (2014) recently showed that arrays of local elements could be grouped together by Gestalt proximity and similarity principles in the absence of participants' awareness. The authors used a visual masking paradigm where subliminally presented primes defined by Gestalt principles of proximity and similarity primed the orientation of subsequent probe stimuli. Schwarzkopf and Rees (2011), on the other hand, studied the integration of separate local elements into global shapes in the absence of awareness by presenting participants with primes defined by position (including corner information) or orientation (with no corner information) cues, which generated square or diamond shapes. Interestingly, the probe could either be defined by the same (within-cue) or different (cross-cue) cues as the prime. Their results showed robust priming effects for both prime types in the visible condition, yet rendering the primes invisible (by counter-phase contrast flickering) produced mixed results: position-defined primes yielded only within-cue priming (suggesting that the local features

produced the effect), whereas orientation-defined primes showed only cross-cue priming (which would suggest that the integration of the local elements into a global shape was taking place). The authors, however, introduced a further control condition for position-defined primes, varying the probe size with the aim to avoid intrinsic lateral connections in a retinotopic level, which might be responsible for the priming effect found with the orientation-defined primes. In this case, only a strong within-cue priming effect was found in the visible condition and no priming effect at all in the invisible condition. Even though these results seem contradictory, Schwarzkopf and Rees concluded that, in the absence of awareness, separate visual stimuli constructed of a small number of local elements did not activate abstract representations of geometric shapes. Interestingly, a previous study using metacontrast masking (Breitmeyer, Ogmen, Ramon and Chen, 2005) showed that square or diamond primes defined only by their corners (the sides of the shapes were removed) would subliminally prime subsequent targets (whole square or diamonds) yet, crucially, square or diamond primes defined only by the sides of the geometric shapes (with no corner information) would produce no priming effects. In sum, the question on whether the integration of local elements into global shapes occurs in the absence of awareness still remains unanswered.

Likewise, the construction of the illusory form under subliminal presentations has originated some controversy among researchers. Illusory form perception -which is often studied using Kanizsa-like stimuli- is a striking example of perceptual organization mechanisms and comprises both modal (i.e. the perception of borders and surfaces across homogeneous luminance regions, usually referred as *illusory contours*) and amodal (i.e. the ability of the visual system to determine which surfaces are hidden behind others, perceiving objects as single continuous entities) completion operations (see Spillmann and Dresch, 1995). While behavioral studies on modal and amodal completions show that, when presented in isolation, they can be completed under the threshold of awareness (Emmanouil & Ro, 2014; Seydell-Greenwald & Schmidt, 2012), a great debate exists, however, on whether the illusory form construction is accomplished early within the visual system hierarchies or, on the contrary, is dependent on higher areas in the visual ventral stream and/or the need of conscious scrutiny for its perception.

Traditionally, Kanizsa configurations have been regarded as examples of perceptual inference, a process that is linked to conscious processing (Vandenbroucke, Fahrenfort, Sligte, & Lamme, 2014). Consistently with that view, early behavioral research using Kanizsa-like stimuli suggested a late processing of the illusory form (Reynolds, 1981; Ringach & Shapley, 1996), yet more recent studies have introduced a variety of subliminal techniques to provide contradictory evidence on the rapid-late processing debate of the illusory form. Using breaking-continuous flash suppression (b-CFS), Wang, Weng, and He (2012) showed that the Kanizsa triangle was significantly faster breaking the suppression time compared to the control stimuli, suggesting that a grouping process leading to the perception of the illusory form was occurring unconsciously. In addition, Lau and Cheung (2012) found that the perception of illusory squares survived the crowding of the inducers, while Poscoliero, Marzi, and Girelli (2013), using meta-contrast visual masking, provided evidence of the illusory salient region - the approximate region without detailed contours that creates a first impression of global surface- being processed unconsciously. In contrast, Harris, Schwarzkopf, Song, Bahrami, and Rees (2011) used continuous flash suppression (CFS) to find that illusory shapes were not perceived in the absence of the awareness of the local inducers. Interestingly, Moors, Wagemans, van Ee & de-Wit (2016) replicated Wang et al.'s (2012) study including further control conditions, finding that the advantage on breaking interocular suppression was not specific to the Kanizsa configuration, which suggests that the Kanizsa surface percept played no role in breakthrough times. It is noteworthy that the use of different techniques to render the stimuli unconscious often influences the results, as some of them allow very little perceptual processing while others use less restrictive masking of the stimuli (see Breitmeyer, 2015; Peremen and Lamy, 2014).

In addition to the behavioral results, physiological and neuroimaging data have provided further contradictory evidence to the debate. While neuronal activations to modal completions (illusory contours) are usually found early within lower-tier cortices (~70 ms, V2 and V1) (Grosf, Shapley & Hawken, 1993; Ohtani et al., 2002; Ramsden, Hung & Roe, 2001; von der Heydt, Peterhans & Baumgartner, 1984), neuroimaging and physiological data on Kanizsa-like illusory form perception produces a complicated picture regarding the *when* - but also the *where* - debate in the illusory form perception (Seghier & Vuilleumier, 2006). Some studies show evidence of early processing of the

illusory form within lower visual cortices (Brodeur et al., 2008; Ffytche, & Zeki, 1996; Larsson et al., 1999; Lee & Nguyen, 2001), but others argue for a later initial processing of the illusory form within higher visual lateral occipital complex (LOC) (Brighina et al., 2003; Halgren, Mendola, Chonag, & Dale, 2003; Knebel & Murray, 2012; Mendola, Dale, Fischl, Liu, & Tootell, 1999; Murray et al., 2002; Shpaner, Murray, & Foxe, 2009). Moreover, some authors suggest a first rough processing of the illusory form (by grouping of the inducers, possibly) in LOC, from which this form segregation may be afterwards sent back to early visual areas for the illusory contour processing (Halgren et al., 2003; Murray et al., 2002; Stanley & Rubin, 2003; Vandenbroucke et al., 2014; Wokke, Vandenbroucke, Scholte, & Lamme, 2012).

Therefore, the present study aims to address two open questions on mid-level perceptual organization processes leading to the perception of global stimuli. First, is the integration of local elements into unified global shapes accomplished without the need of awareness? Second, is the construction of the illusory form completed in the absence of awareness?

For this purpose, we conducted three independent behavioral experiments using a visual masking paradigm in order to shed some light onto these questions. The use of visual masking allowed us to, from a psychophysical point of view, dissociate visuomotor priming effects from conscious perceptual judgments while, additionally, allowing us to infer whether the illusory form perception was being processed without the need of feedback projections from higher to lower visual areas. As previous studies have shown (Fahrenfort, Scholte & Lamme, 2007; Lamme & Roelfsema, 2000), visual masking disrupts reentrant processing from higher to early visual areas, which in our most restrictive experimental conditions might allow us to suppress the possibility of feedback projections from higher (i.e. LOC) to lower visual areas (V1 and V2). Moreover, early feedforward and local recurrent processing within the ventral stream is often associated to perception without awareness, while conscious perception of the stimuli and/or attention are attributed to later, more widespread neural processing, possibly involving frontoparietal areas (Dehaene, Changeux, Naccache, Sackur, & Sergent, 2006; Hochstein & Ahissar, 2002; Lamme, 2006; Wyatte, Jilk, & O'Reilly, 2014).

A key problem in the study of illusory form perception using Kanizsa-like stimuli is that the same shape generated by Kanizsa-like figures might be alternatively perceived by

the grouping of the inducers into a global percept, or even by the separate perception of the local elements at the geometric corners of the shape. Experiments using this type of stimuli often include a control condition, which usually consists of the rotation of the inducers in a way that the illusory figure is no longer perceived (Poscoliero et al., 2013; Wang et al., 2012). Nevertheless, while the local inducers are still placed in identical locations as in the original stimuli, this solution does not seem to solve the possibility of a rough grouping of the inducers or a corner integration of the local elements into the original geometric shape.

With the intention to overcome this problem, we created novel stimuli that could generate two alternative geometric shapes (a square or a diamond) which were presented as primes and could be congruent or incongruent in their shape with subsequent probe stimuli (real squares or diamonds). Moreover, these novel stimuli were divided into three different prime conditions, depending on which perceptual process might account for the geometric shape formation: a *grouping condition* (Fig. 1.a), where the geometric shape was generated by the grouping of the inducers into a global percept; an *illusory condition* (Fig. 1.c), where the shapes were generated by the alignment of some inducers into a Kanizsa-like illusory square or diamond (while the grouping of all the inducers generated a neutral – circular – shape); and a *hybrid condition* (Fig. 1.b), where one of the shapes (i.e. square or diamond) was generated by the grouping of the inducers into a global percept and, at the same time, the alignment of the inducers produced the alternative shape by generating the illusory form. Therefore, whenever an illusory figure was presented as a prime, the grouping of the inducers simultaneously generated the alternative shape (*hybrid condition*) or a neutral shape (*illusory condition*). Prior to that, we conducted a pilot study which showed that the different geometric shapes –by grouping of the inducers and/or by the illusory form perception– were clearly recognizable in all prime conditions.

Insert Figure 1

We set up three experiments: two of them (Experiments 1 and 2) made use of a masking paradigm (with different SOAs) and the third one (Experiment3) consisted of an unmasked procedure. All three experiments were based on the response priming

paradigm (see Schmidt, Haberkamp, & Schmidt, 2011). Both Experiments 1 and 2 (*masked conditions*) were identical in their design: the primes were masked and shown subliminally (prime duration was 27 ms), with the only difference between them being the prime-mask SOA: the first experiment had a 27 ms SOA and the second experiment had a 53 ms SOA. In Experiment 3, the primes were unmasked and presented for the same duration (27 ms), so that they might be consciously perceived by the subjects (*unmasked condition*). Prime-target SOA was kept constant (160 ms) across all experimental conditions. This was an important methodological control, as keeping the prime-target SOA constant through experiments would rule out the possibility of increasing prime-target SOA being responsible for the possible increase in the magnitude of the priming effects (Vorberg, Mattler, Heinecke, Schmidt, & Schwarzbach, 2003). On the other hand, we avoided the presentation of both masked and unmasked primes to the same subjects, while, at the same time, primes were never presented as (visible) targets, which might account for the priming effect as shown in previous studies (Abrams, Klinger, & Greenwald, 2002; Kiesel, Kunde, Pohl, & Hoffmann, 2006; Naccache & Dehaene, 2001; Ortells, Mari-Beffa, & Plaza-Ayllón, 2013; Van den Bussche, Notebaert, & Reynvoet, 2009).

Based on this experimental design, our predictions were as follows: if the integration of local elements into a global shape was completed in the absence of awareness, we expected a response priming effect -measured as shorter response times (RT)- for the *grouping condition* within the *masked condition*. If this integration into a global shape, however, needs participants' awareness of the stimuli, no priming effects were expected in the *masked condition* yet a significant priming effect was expected in the *unmasked condition*.

Likewise, if the illusory form is constructed in the absence of awareness, a priming effect was expected for the *illusory primes* within the *masked condition*. If the illusory form, on the contrary, requires awareness, no priming effects were expected for the *illusory primes* within the *masked condition*, yet significant priming effects were expected for these primes in the *unmasked condition*.

Importantly, the *hybrid condition* primes might provide interesting information on the interactions between grouping operations and the modal and amodal completions that lead to illusory form perception. To our knowledge, this is the first time that two competing responses are assigned to a single prime within a response priming paradigm.

Moreover, the two competing responses arise from different perceptual organization mechanisms, which may differ in both their perceptual strength, as well as in their completion time course within the visual hierarchies. Taking this into consideration, we might expect three different priming scenarios for the *hybrid primes* within the *masked condition*: (1) no priming effects at all if neither the integration of local elements into a global shape (*grouping condition*) nor the illusory form (*illusory condition*) produced any facilitation response in the absence of awareness; conversely, (2) a prime-type-related priming effect if only one of the two operations was unconsciously processed; and (3), if both organization operations were unconsciously processed (i.e. significant priming effects in both the *grouping* and *illusory conditions*) two different priming scenarios might be found: (i) a dominant effect of one of the two stimulus organizations if only the response associated to one organization reaches the motor areas, or alternatively; (ii) a competition for the motor response if both alternative shapes send their associated responses to the motor areas, competition that might affect the response priming magnitude. This reasoning might also apply when the primes were presented unmasked.

Finally, we expected significantly stronger priming effects in the *unmasked condition* as a consequence of the greater visibility of the primes (Desender, & Van den Bussche, 2012; Van den Bussche et al., 2013).

2. Experiment 1. Masked condition SOA 27ms.

In the first experiment, a prime-mask SOA of 27 ms (prime-target SOA of 160 ms) was used to address the possibility of subliminal processing of the primes under a very restrictive masking condition.

2.1. Method

2.1.1. Participants

Twenty-nine undergraduate students (twenty women, age range= 19-58 years, M= 29; SD= 11.8) from the Universidad Nacional de Educación a Distancia (UNED) took part in the experiment. All of them had normal or corrected-to-normal vision and received course credits for their participation.

2.1.2. Stimuli and apparatus

The stimuli were displayed on a 19-in. LCD–LED Samsung 943N color monitor with a 75-Hz refresh rate, a 5:4 aspect ratio and a resolution of 1280 x 1024 controlled by a computer running E-Prime 1.2 software (Psychology Software Tools, 1996–2002). Viewing distance was approximately 57 cm. All the stimuli were displayed in the center of the screen.

As different size of illusory figures has been used in past experiments (length of the size varying from 2° to 10°, see Seghier & Vuilleumier, 2006), we conducted a pilot study in order to explore the optimal prime size that would potentially yield priming effects (results of the pilot study are attached as “supplementary material”).

The *grouping condition primes* consisted of eight black “pacmen” (or inducers) arranged in a way they could produce a square or a diamond shape following the integration of the local elements into a global shape (Fig. 1.a). The size of the diagonals of the diamond was 13.46° and the size of the sides of the square was 10.40°. The *hybrid condition primes* consisted of the same eight inducers arranged in the same spatial location, but four of the inducers were collinearly rotated to produce illusory squares or diamonds (see Fig. 1.b). Crucially, this condition allowed for both the grouping of the inducers into one of the two possible shapes (square or diamond), and at the same time, it generated an illusory form of the opposite shape. The size of the diagonals in the illusory diamond was 7.73°, while the size of the sides in the illusory square was 5.44°. The support ratio (real to illusory-plus-real length) in all cases was 0.5. The *illusory condition primes* consisted of the same eight inducers used to generate the illusory shapes in the two different *hybrid condition primes*, placed in the same spatial locations, so half of them aligned generated the illusory shape while the whole arrangement produced a circular (neutral to the RT task) shape by the grouping of the inducers, (see Fig. 1.c), which served as a neutral grouping condition. The size of the circle diameter was 10.40°. All the inducers used in the three prime conditions were identical, subtending a visual angle of 2.67°. All the primes were composed of the same amount of inducers (eight).

Pattern masks were of circular shape and also composed of “pacmen”, but of smaller size (1.61°) and randomly rotated by 90°, 180° or 270°. The shape of the masks was circular – therefore neutral to the subsequent shape discrimination task – in order to control the possibility of priming effects being caused by the presentation of the mask. Twelve different masks were generated by rotating the patterns in different ways, and

were randomly assigned as first, second or third mask in the stimuli sequence. In each trial, all three masks were always different.

The target stimuli consisted of solid or striped square or diamond shapes. All the target stimuli were composed of a small shape – which was the same size of the illusory shape in the primes– inside a big shape, which was the size of the external boundary of the grouped inducers in the primes. Both small and big shapes were always congruent. Twenty-four different target stimuli were generated by varying lightness (clear, grey or dark) and the filling of the shapes (solid or striped) in order to force participants to base their response on the specific shape of the stimulus regardless of its physical appearance. All the stimuli were generated using Adobe Illustrator CS5.

2.2. Procedure and design

Participants performed three consecutive tasks: 1) a masked priming task and 2) two prime visibility discrimination tasks, the three of them completed individually in a dimly lit room with a five-minute break between tasks. In the masked priming task, participants had to carry out a forced-choice reaction time (RT) task. Participants were told that they would see two different geometrical shapes (square or diamond) displayed on the screen, and that they would have to indicate, as fast as possible but avoiding making mistakes, the specific shape that had appeared in each trial by pressing one of two response buttons in the number pad (number 1= square, number 2= diamond) with their index and middle fingers of the dominant hand. Moreover, participants were not told about the masked primes, but were merely informed that each trial would begin with the presentation of a “flash signal”, which would warn them that the target stimulus was going to appear afterwards.

Insert Figure 2

The sequence of events in any masked priming trial in Experiment 1 is depicted in Fig. 2. Each trial started with a mask pattern (80 ms) followed by a priming stimuli which could belong to either the *grouping condition*, the *hybrid condition* or the *illusory condition* (27 ms, all conditions counterbalanced), the inter-stimulus interval (ISI) stimuli in this condition was 0 ms (non-present), so the prime was followed by the second mask pattern (always different from the first one, displayed during 80 ms) and a

third mask pattern (always different from the first and second masks, 53 ms). After this “flash”, the target stimulus appeared and remained until response. There was an 800 ms pause after the end of each trial and before the start of the next trial. A practice block with 32 trials preceded the six experimental blocks, of 96 trials each, yielding a total of 576 experimental trials (one half congruent trials and one half incongruent ones). Feedback was provided only for the practice trials.

Immediately after the end of the priming task, participants were fully informed of the nature of the “flash signal” and all the primes were shown on a projector screen until all participants clearly understood the different geometric forms that could be generated in the three different prime conditions. Then, they were asked to perform two different forced-choice prime discrimination tasks designed to obtain an objective index of the visibility of the primes. In the first task, consisting of 24 practice trials followed by 2 blocks of 96 trials each, with a total of 192 trials, participants were instructed to pay attention to the masked primes and to try to discriminate between square or diamond shapes that were generated only by the grouping of the inducers. Therefore, in this first discrimination task only *grouping condition primes* and *hybrid primes* were displayed, but participants were carefully instructed to discriminate the shape generated by the grouping of the inducers whenever the *hybrid primes* appeared. The sequence of events, on the other hand, was identical to that of the priming task, with the following exceptions: 1) the target stimuli were displayed during a fixed time of 500 ms, 2) after the target offset, two rectangles including the two response options (“square”, “diamond”) were displayed on the screen so that participants could provide their response by clicking the mouse on the selected rectangle without response time demand; and 3) the trials were self-administered in order to ensure that participants were as ready as possible to discriminate the masked prime. Participants were instructed to try to be as accurate as possible and to guess on trials in which they could not identify the primes.

The second discrimination task consisted of the same trials and blocks as the first one, but participants were now instructed to pay attention to the masked primes and to try to discriminate the illusory square or diamond shapes that were generated by the rotation of some of the inducers. Therefore, in the second discrimination task only *hybrid condition primes* and *illusory primes* were displayed, while participants were carefully instructed to discriminate the illusory shape in the *hybrid condition primes*. Half of the

participants passed the grouping discrimination task first and the illusory shape discrimination task afterwards, while the other half of the participants passed the tasks in the reverse sequence.

2.3. Results

2.3.1. Priming task

Mean accuracy (correct responses) oscillated between 97% and 98% across all conditions (Prime condition: Grouping, Hybrid, Illusory; Congruency: Congruent vs. Incongruent). Individual accuracy performance was between 93% and 100% (correct responses). Given that the participants' responses were highly accurate (average error rate was 2%) only data on RTs was analyzed.

Mean RTs for correct responses were submitted to a 3 (Prime condition: Grouping vs. Hybrid vs. Illusory) x 2 (Congruency: Congruent vs. Incongruent) ANOVA. Short and long RTs (shorter than 200 ms and longer than 1500 ms) were excluded from the analysis. The analysis showed a marginally significant main effect for Congruency, $F(1,28) = 3.3$, $MSe = 303.8$, $p = .079$, $\eta^2_p = .11$. No first or second order interaction effects were found between factors.

Insert Table 1

2.3.2. Prime visibility discrimination tasks

When asked informally after completing the priming task, none of the participants reported having seen any geometric shape patterns before the presentation of the target. This suggests that participants had no subjective awareness of the primes.

Mean accuracy in the prime visibility discrimination tasks was .51 (SD = .04, individual rates from .43 to .58) for the *grouping condition* primes and .55 (SD = .06, individual rates from .44 to .77) for the *illusory condition* primes. Equivalently, direct measures of prime visibility (d') were calculated for each participant, by treating one level (i.e., square) as signal and the other level (i.e., diamond) as noise. The individual d' values for the *grouping condition* primes ranged between -.34 and .40 and the overall mean

was .04 (SD = .21). The individual d' values for the *illusory condition* primes ranged between -.33 and 1.53 and the overall mean was .28 (SD = .34).

Individual chi square tests were conducted for each participant as a measure of signal detection sensitivity by computing each possible response (Hit, False Alarm, Miss or Correct Rejection) into a 2x2 contingency table, which is equivalent to test the hypothesis $d' = 0$. Results for the *grouping primes* showed that only 3 participants were discriminating above strict chance level (all $\chi^2(1) \leq 4.775$, all $.029 \leq p \leq .041$), while the combined chi squares ($\chi^2(29) = 38.142$, $p = .119$) suggested a group discrimination of $d' = 0$. Results for the *illusory primes* showed that 7 participants discriminated the primes above strict chance level (all $4.775 \leq \chi^2(1) \leq 56.397$, all $.001 < p \leq .029$), while the combined chi squares were $\chi^2(29) = 144.005$, $p < .001$, suggesting that the group discrimination was not at strict chance level.

Insert Figure 3 and Figure 4

Overall, results showed that the primes in the *grouping condition* were discriminated at $d' = 0$. On the other hand, combined results for the *illusory primes* were not at strict chance level, due to some participants' sensitivity measures being above 0 in the *illusory condition*.

2.4. Discussion

Experiment 1 showed that none of the primes (*grouping*, *hybrid* or *illusory*) produced any significant priming effect. Therefore, a stimulus duration of 27 ms immediately followed by a mask (SOA 27 ms) seems to be a very restrictive condition to allow enough processing of the prime to produce any motor response facilitation, and therefore a priming effect, in the subsequent shape discrimination task.

3. Experiment 2. Masked condition SOA 53 ms.

In the second experiment, we introduced an ISI of 27 ms in order to increase the prime-mask SOA to 53 ms, with the intention to continue the study of the subliminal processing of the primes under restrictive masking conditions.

3.1. Method

3.1.1. Participants

Thirty-four undergraduate students (twenty-eight women, age range= 19-65years, $M=34$; $SD=12.7$) from the UNED participated in the experiment. All of them had normal or corrected-to-normal vision and received course credits for their participation.

3.1.2. Stimuli and apparatus

The stimuli and apparatus were identical to those on Experiment 1.

3.2. Procedure and design

The experimental procedure was the same as in Experiment 1, but a different prime-mask SOA was used, introducing an inter-stimulus interval (ISI) of 27 ms (prime-mask SOA of 53 ms). Prime-target SOA was kept constant on 160 ms by reducing the duration of the second backward masks to 27 ms.

Insert Figure 5

3.3. Results

3.3.1. Priming task

Mean accuracy (correct responses) was 98% in all the conditions (Prime condition: Grouping, Hybrid, Illusory; Congruency: Congruent vs. Incongruent). Individual accuracy performance oscillated between 94% and 100% (correct responses). Given that the participants responses were highly accurate (average error rate was 2%), only data on RTs was analyzed.

Mean RTs for correct responses were submitted to a 3 (Prime condition: Grouping vs. Hybrid vs. Illusory) x 2 (Congruency: Congruent vs. Incongruent) ANOVA. Short and long RTs (shorter than 200 ms and longer than 1500 ms) were excluded from the analysis. The analysis showed no effect for Prime Type, a significant main effect for Congruency, $F(1,33) = 9.3$, $MSe = 284.5$, $p = .04$, $\eta^2_p = .22$, showing that RTs on congruent trials were significantly shorter (564 ms) than those on incongruent trials (571 ms). A marginally significant interactive first order effect between Prime Type and Congruency was found, $F(1,32) = 3.1$, $MSe = 334.2$, $p = .066$, $\eta^2_p = .09$. A closer

inspection of the data showed that significant differences between congruent and incongruent conditions only occurred in the *grouping condition* ($\Delta 13$ ms; $p < .001$) and in the *illusory condition* ($\Delta 9$ ms; $p = .002$). No priming effect was found for the *hybrid condition* primes ($\Delta 1$ ms; $p = .954$).

Insert Table 2

3.3.2. Prime visibility discrimination task

When asked informally after completing the priming task, none of the participants reported having seen any geometric shape patterns before the presentation of the target. This suggests that participants had no subjective awareness of the primes.

Mean accuracy in the prime visibility discrimination tasks was .50 (SD = .03, individual rates from .44 to .57) for the *grouping condition* primes and .55 (SD = .08, individual rates from .48 to .86) for the *illusory condition* primes. As in Experiment 1, a direct measure of prime visibility (d') was calculated for each participant. The individual d' values for the *grouping condition* primes ranged between -.36 and .38 and the overall mean was .01 (SD = .16). The individual d' values for the *illusory condition* primes ranged between -.11 and 2.17 and the overall mean was .27 (SD = .48).

Individual chi square tests were conducted for each participant as a measure of signal detection sensitivity by computing each possible response (Hit, False Alarm, Miss or Correct Rejection) into a 2x2 contingency table, which is equivalent to test the hypothesis $d' = 0$. Results for the *grouping primes* showed that only 1 participant was discriminating above strict chance level ($\chi^2(1) = 4.200, p \leq .05$), while the combined chi squares ($\chi^2(34) = 24.169, p = .894$) suggested a group discrimination of $d' = 0$. Results for the *illusory primes* showed that only 6 participants discriminated the primes above strict chance level (all $6.216 \leq \chi^2(1) \leq 99.457$, all $.001 < p \leq .013$), while the combined chi squares were $\chi^2(34) = 233.492, p < .001$, suggesting that the group discrimination was not at strict chance level.

In order to confirm that the priming effect obtained for *illusory primes* was not due to 6 participants performing above strict chance level in the discrimination task, we conducted a further RT analysis for those 28 participants (twenty-four women, age

range= 19-65years, M= 34; SD= 12.8) that discriminated at strict chance level. Therefore, mean RTs for correct responses were submitted to a 3 (Prime condition: Grouping vs. Hybrid vs. Illusory) x 2 (Congruency: Congruent vs. Incongruent) ANOVA. Short and long RTs (shorter than 200 ms and longer than 1500 ms) were excluded from the analysis. The analysis showed a significant main effect for Congruency, $F(1,27) = 7.3$, $MSe = 328.9$, $p = .012$, $\eta^2_p = .21$, showing that RTs on congruent trials were significantly shorter (580 ms) than those on incongruent trials (588 ms). A closer inspection of the data showed that significant differences between congruent and incongruent conditions occurred for *illusory primes* ($\Delta 10$ ms; $p = .002$) but not for the *hybrid primes* ($\Delta -1$ ms; $p = .920$).

Insert Figure 6 and Figure 7

Overall, discrimination results showed that the primes in the *grouping condition* were strictly at $d' = 0$. On the other hand, 6 participants' sensitivity measures were above 0 in the *illusory condition*. Further statistical analysis for *illusory primes* showed that the significant priming effects obtained for this condition were obtained when the primes were discriminated at $d' = 0$

3.4. Discussion

Contrary to the results obtained in Experiment 1, Experiment 2 showed significant subliminal priming effects for both *grouping* ($\Delta 13$ ms; $p < .001$) and *illusory primes* ($\Delta 9$ ms; $p = .002$). Interestingly, *hybrid primes* did not yield any significant priming effects ($\Delta 1$ ms; $p = .954$). As for our initial predictions, if both grouping and illusory primes yielded significant priming effects, two different priming scenarios might be expected: (i) a dominant effect of one of the two stimulus organizations if only the response associated to one organization reaches the motor areas, or alternatively; (ii) a competition for the motor response if both alternative shapes send their associated responses to the motor areas, competition that might affect the response priming magnitude. Results in this condition suggest that both alternative shapes representations reach the motor areas and compete for the response facilitation, following the second possible scenario.

4. Combined analysis of Experiments 1 and 2

A combined analysis of Experiment 1 and Experiment 2 was conducted in order to confirm the difference in the pattern of results found in Experiment 1 and Experiment 2, where *experiment* was considered as a between-subjects factor. Beyond the apparent dissimilarity between experiments, we estimated that a direct comparison between Experiment 1 and Experiment 2 by means of a mixed ANOVA would allow us to clearly establish a significant difference between both patterns of results.

Mean RTs were submitted to a mixed ANOVA with SOA conditions (2 levels: 27 ms or 53 ms) as between-subjects factor and Prime condition (Grouping vs. Hybrid vs. Illusory) and Congruency (Congruent vs. Incongruent) as within-subjects factors. Results showed a significant interaction between SOA condition and Congruency, $F(1,63) = 8.1$, $p = .006$, $\eta^2_p = .12$. Additionally, a significant three-way interaction between SOA condition, Congruency and Prime Type was found, $F(1,63) = 4.05$, $p = .020$, $\eta^2_p = .06$. These significant interactions are compatible with a different pattern of results associated to the SOA values of each experiment. To decompose these interactions, further ANOVAs could be performed separately for each group. However, these analyses have been already performed and reported above in the individual analysis of each experiment.

5. Experiment 3. Unmasked primes.

In Experiment 3, both forward and backward masks were removed in order to allow a supraliminal processing of the primes. Prime presentation duration was still 27 ms, while prime target SOA was kept to 160 ms by introducing an ISI of 133 ms.

5.1. Method

5.1.1. Participants

Twenty undergraduate students (thirteen women, age range= 19-34 years, $M = 24$; $SD = 4.8$) from the UNED participated in the experiment. All of them had normal or corrected-to-normal vision and received course credits for their participation.

5.1.2. Stimuli and apparatus

The stimuli and apparatus were identical to those on Experiments 1 and 2.

5.2. Procedure and design

The experimental procedure was the same as in Experiment 1 and 2 with an important exception: no masks were used in this experiment. Prime target SOA was kept to 160

ms by introducing an ISI of 133 ms.

Insert Figure 8

5.3. Results

5.3.1. Priming task

Mean accuracy (correct responses) oscillated between 93% and 97% across all the conditions (Prime condition: Grouping, Hybrid, Illusory; Congruency: Congruent vs. Incongruent). Individual accuracy performance oscillated between 86% and 100% (correct responses). Given that the participants responses were highly accurate (average error rate was 4%), only data on RTs was analyzed.

Mean RTs for correct responses were submitted to a 3 (Prime condition: Grouping vs. Hybrid vs. Illusory) x 2 (Congruency: Congruent vs. Incongruent) ANOVA. Short and long RTs (shorter than 200 ms and longer than 1500 ms) were excluded from the analysis. This analysis showed a significant main effect for Congruency, $F(1,19) = 7.9$, $MSe = 337.7$, $p = .011$, $\eta^2_p = .29$, showing that RTs on congruent trials were significantly shorter (520 ms) than those on incongruent trials (529 ms). A significant interactive first order effect between Prime Type and Congruency was found, $F(1,19) = 50.4$, $MSe = 355.2$, $p < .001$, $\eta^2_p = .73$. Pairwise comparisons using Bonferroni correction showed that significant differences between congruent and incongruent conditions occurred in all prime type conditions: *grouping condition* ($\Delta 50$ ms; $p < .001$), *hybrid condition* ($\Delta 34$ ms; $p < .001$; priming effect due to the grouping of the inducers) and *illusory condition* ($\Delta 12$ ms; $p = .045$).

Insert Table 3

Further *t*-test comparisons were carried out between the priming effects in the three different Prime Type conditions. Results showed that: there was a marginally significant difference between priming effects for the *grouping condition* and the *hybrid condition* ($t(19) = 2.040$; $p = .056$) and significant priming effect differences between *grouping*

condition and the *illusory condition* ($t(19) = 4.374; p < .001$) and between the *hybrid condition* and the *illusory condition* ($t(19) = 2.596; p = .018$), being the relations of the magnitude effect: *grouping primes* > *hybrid primes* > *illusory primes*.

5.3.2. Prime visibility discrimination task

When asked informally after completing the priming task, participants reported having seen some patterns before the presentation of the target. This suggests that participants had some subjective awareness of the primes.

Mean accuracy in the prime visibility discrimination tasks were .89 (SD = .17, individual rates from .50 to 1) for the *grouping condition* primes and .84 (SD = .21, individual rates from .33 to 1) for the *illusory condition* primes. As in Experiment 1 and 2, a direct measure of prime visibility (d') was calculated for each participant. The individual d' values for the *grouping condition* primes ranged between .00 and 4.62 and the overall mean was 3.21 (SD = 1.56). The individual d' values for the *illusory condition* primes ranged between -.90 and 4.62 and the overall mean was 2.81 (SD = 1.76).

Individual chi square tests were conducted again for each participant. Results for the *grouping primes* showed that only 3 participants were discriminating the primes at chance level (all $.001 \leq \chi^2(1) \leq .528$, all $p \geq .468$), while the combined chi squares ($\chi^2(21) = 2855.777, p < .001$) showed that the *grouping primes* were largely visible.

Results for the *illusory primes* showed that only 2 participants were discriminating the primes at chance level (all $.573 \leq \chi^2(1) \leq 22.889$, all $p \geq .449$), while the combined chi squares ($\chi^2(21) = 2562.148, p < .001$) showed that discrimination performance was clearly above chance level, suggesting that *illusory primes* were also largely visible in the main task.

Insert Figure 9 and Figure 10

In sum, these results overall suggest that the primes in the unmasked condition were largely visible.

5.4. Discussion

Experiment 3 showed that, when presented unmasked, all three prime conditions

(*grouping*, *hybrid* and *illusory*) produced significant priming effects. Interestingly, *grouping* and *hybrid* primes produced significantly stronger priming ($\Delta 50$ ms; $p < .001$ and $\Delta 34$ ms; $p < .001$) compared to those produced by the *illusory primes* ($\Delta 12$ ms; $p = .045$). On the other hand, priming effects in the *hybrid condition* seemed consistent with results in Experiment 2, suggesting a competition of response facilitation as a result of both stimulus organizations reaching the motor areas.

6. General Discussion

Is the integration of local elements into unified global shapes and/or the construction of the illusory form accomplished without the need of awareness?

In order to answer these questions, we conducted three experiments in which participants were presented with masked (Experiment 1, SOA = 27ms; Experiment 2; SOA = 53ms) and unmasked (Experiment 3) primes that could be congruent or incongruent in their shape with a subsequent probe stimuli (real squares or diamonds).

The subliminal nature of the priming effects within the *masked condition* was explored by objective visibility measures: while informal subjective reports from the participants suggested an absence of awareness of the masked primes, objective results showed that the discrimination of the *grouping primes* was at $d' = 0$ and, on the other hand, combined chi square sensitivity measures were above 0 in the *illusory condition*. Further statistical analysis for *illusory primes* showed that the significant priming effects obtained for this condition were obtained when the primes were discriminated at $d' = 0$

According to our predictions for the *grouping* primes, if the integration of local elements into a global shape was completed in the absence of awareness, we would expect a response priming effect for the *grouping primes* within the *masked condition*. That is exactly what we found: even though no significant priming effects were found in Experiment 1 (SOA of 27 ms), which might be a very restrictive condition for the processing of the masked stimuli to influence subsequent motor responses, significant priming effects ($\Delta 13$ ms) were found for the *grouping* condition with a longer SOA (Experiment 2, SOA 53 ms). How does this result integrate within the existing evidence? On the one hand, they are consistent with previous research on perceptual grouping operations being accomplished under the threshold of awareness (Emmanouil & Ro, 2014; Montoro et al., 2014; Breitmeyer et al., 2005). On the other hand, they

provide new evidence of the integration of local visual features into a global shape in the absence of awareness. Indeed, our data suggests that local elements can group together into a global shape in the absence of awareness, result that seems to contradict Schwarzkopf and Rees' (2011) previous findings. In addition, the strong priming effects found for the *grouping primes* in the *unmasked condition* ($\Delta 50$ ms) showed that, when presented unmasked, the grouping of the local elements was able to produce a strong global percept, while, at the same time, these results provide evidence that the primes were successful in producing facilitation response priming.

On the other hand, if the illusory form was constructed in the absence of awareness, we would expect a priming effect for the *illusory condition* primes within the *masked condition*. If the construction of the illusory form, on the contrary, required awareness, we would expect no priming effects for the *illusory primes* within the *masked condition*, but significant priming effect for these primes in the *unmasked condition*. The former is what we found: even though no significant priming effects were found in Experiment 1 (SOA of 27 ms), which again seems a very restrictive condition for the processing of the masked stimuli to influence subsequent motor responses; significant subliminal priming effects ($\Delta 9$ ms) were found for the *illusory condition* in Experiment 2.

Importantly, this unconscious priming effect provides new evidence to the ongoing debate on the possibility of unconscious processing of illusory figures, evidence which is in line with previous studies suggesting a subliminal processing of the illusory figures (Wang et al., 2012; Lau & Cheung, 2012; Poscoliero et al., 2013). Results in the *unmasked condition*, on the other hand, showed a significant priming effect for the *illusory condition* ($\Delta 12$ ms), interestingly of similar magnitude to the *masked* (SOA 53 ms) *condition* ($\Delta 9$ ms)¹.

From a neurophysiological point of view, our experimental design may allow us to disentangle the need of feedback projections from higher to lower visual areas in the perception of illusory figures. According to the most widely held view, initial feedforward processing of visual information is independent of visibility for about 100-120 ms. During that time, it proceeds irrespective of whether the information is backward-masked at a later point in time (e.g., Breitmeyer, Ro, & Singhal, 2004;

¹ An independent samples t-test was carried out to compare priming results for *illusory primes* between *masked* SOA53 condition and *unmasked condition*, being $t(27.12) = -.528$, $p = .602$, therefore yielding no significant differences between conditions.

Fahrenfort, Scholte, & Lamme, 2007; Lamme & Roelfsema, 2000). Masking, though, would play a role in later, reentrant processing of stimulus information, from a latency of 100-120 ms after stimulus onset onwards (Boehler, Schoenfeld, Heinze, & Hopf, 2008; Liu, Agam, Madsen, & Kreiman, 2009). While electroencephalographic (EEG) and magneto-encephalographic (MEG) recordings usually show illusory contour (IC) sensitivity effects within LOC at 85–155 ms post-stimulus onset (Halgren et al., 2003; Knebel & Murray, 2012; Murray et al., 2002; Murray, Imber, Javitt, & Foxe 2006; Shpaner et al., 2009), the introduction of a mask stimulus as early as 53 ms after stimulus onset (Experiment 2) should allow us to suppress feedback information from LOC to early visual areas V1 and V2 related to the processing of the primes. The subliminal priming results found in Experiment 2 for *illusory primes* therefore suggest an early construction of the illusory shape, without the need of feedback projections from higher order to early visual areas. Interestingly, the similar magnitude priming effects in both the *masked* and *unmasked conditions*, is consistent with the fact that feedback projections from higher to lower visual areas are not crucial in the construction of the illusory form (yet the absence of priming magnitude differences for *illusory primes* between visibility conditions is discussed in more depth below).

However, we cannot categorically dismiss alternative mechanisms by which the visual masking might be operating. It may possible that early pattern mask is reducing the bottom-up signal from the primes, leading to a weaker feedforward sweep, or the mask may follow the initial feedforward sweep containing prime information increasing the feature noise within the information processing (see Enns & Di Lollo, 2000, for a review). For example, Agaoglu, Agaoglu, Breitmeyer, & Ogmen (2015) recently suggested that the mask reduces the target's signal-to-noise ratio (SNR) by (i) suppressing or interrupting the signal of the target in para-/meta-contrast, (ii) by increasing noise in pattern masking by noise, and (iii) a combination of the two in pattern masking by structure.

Interestingly, no priming effects were found for *hybrid primes* within the *masked condition*, yet significant priming effects were found when the primes were presented unmasked. How could these results be interpreted? On the one hand, the two competing responses associated to the *hybrid primes* arise from two different perceptual organization mechanisms, which may differ in both their perceptual strength, as well as in their completion time course within the initial visual hierarchies. On the other hand,

results in both masked Experiment 2 (SOA 53 ms) and unmasked Experiment 3 may be especially informative to explore the dynamics of visuomotor response competition as, according to our initial predictions, if both *grouping* and *illusory primes* produced significant priming effects (as it turned out to be), we might expect a dominant effect of the related stimulus organization if only the response associated to one stimulus organization reaches the motor areas, or alternatively, a competition for the motor response if both alternative shapes send their associated responses to motor areas. In line with the latter, the absence of a priming effect for the *hybrid primes* in the *masked condition* would suggest that the response associated to both alternative shapes reach the motor areas and engage in a competition for the response facilitation, which eventually produces a cancellation of both responses. Interestingly, the significantly different priming magnitudes found for *grouping* and *illusory primes* in the *unmasked condition* (*grouping primes* = Δ 50 ms, *illusory primes* = Δ 12 ms; Δ 38 ms larger priming effects for the *grouping primes*) may shed some light into the nature of this competition for response in the motor areas. The priming effects found in the *unmasked condition* seems to be consistent with the former explanation of competition for the motor response, while suggesting that this competition follows a subtractive pattern. This subtractive pattern of response facilitation would be consistent with (i) the strongest perceptual completion (the grouping of the local elements) being responsible of the priming effect; and (ii) the priming magnitude (Δ 34 ms) in the unmasked *hybrid condition* equating rather accurately the subtraction of priming effects for the two different organizations in isolation (i.e. *grouping primes* and *illusory primes*; *difference* Δ 38 ms). Furthermore, this subtraction of the response facilitations hypothesis would also fit the results in the *masked condition*, as the priming effects for the two stimulus organizations in isolation (*grouping* and *illusory shapes*) were of similar magnitude, therefore cancelling each other out. However, these are tentative explanations that have to be cautiously interpreted. Indeed, our results come from the aggregation of individual performances, and individual differences in visual masking are actually a matter of debate (see Bachmann & Francis, 2013). The origin of these differences should be carefully explored in the future. An also interesting question for future research, the identification of the neural underpinnings of the competing levels of form perception and the related motor response activations would be of much interest. In this regard, ERP data could shed some light into the time course of the different readiness potentials associated to the different motor activations on an individual level.

It seems clear, on the other hand, that when presented unmasked, the global shape that arises from the integration of the local elements forms a stronger percept. Why did this grouping of local elements produce stronger priming effects within the *unmasked condition*? Looking to the nature of the prime stimuli, the grouping of the local elements into a global percept may be explained as a global –or coarse– cue processed at low spatial frequencies (LSF), while the construction of the illusory form would respond to a finer, more detailed processing possibly involving high spatial frequencies (HSF) (De Valois & De Valois, 1990; Hughes, Nozawa, & Kitterle, 1996). The dominance of global over local spatial cues in the *unmasked condition* might be attributed to either a faster processing of lower spatial frequencies (Breitmeyer, 1975; Harwerth and Levi 1978), or to an inhibition of high-frequency mechanisms by those tuned to lower spatial frequencies (e.g., DeValois 1977; Tolhurst 1972). Alternatively, if the motor response activation is being influenced by the *contour* of the two opposing shapes, the stroke of the contour in the grouping conditions is significantly larger (i.e., the size of the inducers, 2.67°) to the stroke of the illusory contour.

Results for *illusory primes*, on the other hand, leave an interesting question open to debate. Why did we find no significant priming magnitude differences between *masked* and *unmasked* conditions? Previous research using Kanizsa-like stimuli as unmasked primes has shown that these stimuli can yield significant priming effects (Barlasov-Ioffe and Hochstein, 2009). On the other hand, results obtained by Breitmeyer et al. (2005) show that when the primes are visible, partial forms may act as stronger primes than whole forms. In line with that later result, we find stronger priming effects for primes composed of partial forms (*grouping* primes) as opposed to those perceived as whole forms (*illusory* shapes). An alternative explanation, however, may be related to the different nature of the *grouping* and *illusory* primes. While *grouping condition* primes generated only one geometric shape (i.e. square or diamond), *illusory condition* primes may generate two different geometric shapes simultaneously: a priming illusory shape (square or diamond) by the alignment of four of the eight inducers; and a neutral (circular) shape by the grouping of all the inducers into a global shape. Looking to the apparent response interference between alternative shapes simultaneously presented (as shown for *hybrid* primes), a possible explanation for these *illusory condition* results might suggest an attenuation of the priming effects due to the grouping of the inducers into the circular (neutral to the subsequent RT task) shape. Furthermore, differences in

priming effects might also be due to differences in prime and target size between *grouping* primes and *illusory primes* (Seghier & Vuilleumier, 2006): the size of the *grouping* primes was always larger (the diagonals of the diamond were 13.46° and the size of the sides of the square were 10.40°) compared to the size of the *illusory* primes (diagonals were 7.73° and the size of the sides were 5.44°). This fact may result in a size-facilitation effect (i.e. bigger primes would yield larger priming effects), which would be an interesting question for future research.

Finally, our results also provide some evidence on the relation between prime visibility and priming magnitudes. The differences in priming magnitude found between *masked* and *unmasked conditions* (Fig. 7) suggest that the magnitude of the priming effects is somehow related to prime awareness (Desender, & Van den Bussche, 2012; Van den Bussche et al., 2013). By keeping the prime-target SOA constant (at 160 ms) in all three experiments, we ruled out the interpretation of increasing prime-target SOA being responsible for the increase in the magnitude of the priming effects (Vorberg et al. 2003). The magnitude of the priming effects, however, were significantly larger for the *grouping* and *hybrid primes* in the *unmasked condition* ($\Delta 50$ ms and $\Delta 34$ ms respectively) compared to the *masked condition* ($\Delta 13$ ms and $\Delta 1$ ms respectively)², results that seem to be in line with the hypothesis that visibility of the primes is related to priming magnitude. Yet, our data does not allow us to suggest a direct causal relation between visibility and priming magnitude. The stronger priming results in our experiment were achieved by removing the mask patterns from the sequence of stimuli. While greater discrimination performances for masked stimuli might not produce greater priming effects, the removal of the masking seems to allow stronger congruent and incongruent responses arriving to the motor areas, possibly as a result of reentrant processing of the primes and/or the elimination of noise from the initial feedforward sweep, therefore producing greater priming effects within the *unmasked condition*.

Insert Figure 11

² Again, independent samples t-test were carried out to compare priming results between *masked* and *unmasked conditions*, being the results for the *grouping primes*: $t(52) = -5.795$, $p < .001$ and for the *hybrid primes*: $t(52) = -4.026$, $p < .001$, therefore, significantly different in both cases.

Conclusions

In sum, our results support the possibility of the integration of local visual features into a global shape in the absence of awareness and, likewise, the construction of the illusory form without awareness. From a neurophysiological point of view, our experimental design allowed us to disentangle the need of feedback projections from higher to lower visual areas in the perception of illusory figures, our results suggesting that feedback projections from higher to lower visual areas are not crucial in the construction of the illusory form.

Overall, our results are in line with previous studies showing that perceptual organization operations occur in the absence of awareness while, at the same time, they provide compelling evidence on shape completion operations from local elements being subliminally accomplished.

Acknowledgments

This research did not receive any specific grant from funding agencies in the public, commercial, or not-for-profit sectors.

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Figure 1. Prime conditions.

Figure 2: Stimuli and sequence of events Experiment 1: a) Primes b) example of Probe Types

Fig 2. Stimuli and sequence of events in Experiment 1: a) Prime types; b) example of Probe types

Table 1: Mean (SD) RTs (in ms) for the congruent and incongruent trials in Experiment 1, and the amount of priming (incongruent-congruent) as a function of Prime Type.

RT results Experiment 1			
Prime Type	Congruent	Incongruent	Priming Effect
Grouping	559 (87.1)	554 (74.5)	-5
Hybrid	552 (80.3)	555 (71.8)	3
<i>Congruent = grouping con/ illusory incon</i>			
Illusory	562 (84.6)	555 (79.5)	-7

Figure 3. Relation between d' scores and priming effect for the *grouping primes* in Experiment 1 (SOA27 ms). Mean response priming effect and 95% confident intervals are shown.

Figure 4. Relation between d' scores and priming effect for the *illusory primes* in Experiment 1 (SOA27 ms). Mean response priming effect and 95% confident intervals are shown.

Fig. 5. Stimuli and sequence of events Experiment 2 a) Prime types b) example of Probe types.

Fig 3. Stimuli and sequence of events in Experiment 2: a) Prime types; b) example of Probe types

Table 2: Mean (SD) RTs (in ms) for the congruent and incongruent trials in Experiment 2, and the amount of priming (incongruent-congruent) as a function of Prime Type.

Prime Type	RT results Experiment 2		Priming Effect
	Congruent	Incongruent	
Grouping	560 (81.9)	573 (84.2)	13***
Hybrid	569 (97.1)	570 (87.8)	1
<i>Congruent = grouping con/ illusory incon</i> Illusory	562 (92.5)	571 (91.9)	9*

* $p < .05$

*** $p < .001$

Figure 6. Relation between d' scores and priming effect for the *grouping primes* in Experiment 2 (SOA53 ms). Mean response priming effect and 95% confident intervals are shown.

Figure 7. Relation between d' scores and priming effect for the *illusory primes* in Experiment 2 (SOA53 ms). Mean response priming effect and 95% confident intervals are shown.

Fig. 8. Stimuli and sequence of events Experiment 3 a) Prime types b) example of Probe types.

Table 3: Mean (SD) RTs (in ms) for the congruent and incongruent trials in Experiment 3, and the amount of priming (incongruent-congruent) as a function of Prime Type.

RT results Experiment 3			
Prime Type	Congruent	Incongruent	Priming Effect
Grouping	498 (90.0)	549 (94.8)	50***
Hybrid	506 (97.7)	540 (86.6)	34***
<i>Congruent = grouping con/ illusory incon</i> Illusory	520 (89.3)	532 (91.8)	12*

* $p < .05$

*** $p < .001$

Figure 9. Relation between d' scores and priming effect for the *grouping primes* in Experiment 3 (unmasked). Mean response priming effect and 95% confident intervals are shown.

Figure 10. Relation between d' scores and priming effect for the *illusory condition* in Experiment 3 (unmasked). Mean response priming effect and 95% confident intervals are shown.

Figure 11. Priming magnitudes (in ms) for each prime type across experiments.

Fig 7. Priming magnitudes (in ms) for each prime type across experiments.